

Experimental

Preparation of complex: Potassiumpentacyanonitrosylchromate(I) hydrate (1.0 g) was dissolved in water (30 ml) and to it an aqueous solution of sodiumdiethyldithiocarbamate (1.0 g) was added. Acetic acid (1 : 1, 10 ml) was then slowly added with constant stirring and the issuing gas chased by a current of carbon dioxide, whereby a reddish brown precipitate appeared which was filtered and washed several times with water. The precipitate was extracted with acetone and the reddish brown compound was reprecipitated by adding petroleum ether and dried (35%), (Found: Cr, 13.2; C, 30.1; N, 10.5; H, 5.56; mol. wt. 410. $\text{CrNO}(\text{DTC})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ requires Cr, 13.1; C, 30.3; N, 10.6; H, 5.5%; mol. wt. 396).

Analysis: Chromium was determined as Cr_2O_3 after decomposing the complex by heating with alkali followed by dissolution in nitric acid and precipitating by NH_4OH . Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically.

Physical methods: Conductance was measured in analytical grade methanol using a dip type cell on a Philips conductivity bridge. Molecular weight of the compound was determined by Rast's method using camphor as solvent. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on powdered sample using Gouy balance. The apparatus was calibrated using cobalt mercury thiocyanate. The parallel and perpendicular components of the 'g' value were obtained on powdered sample using potassium bromide as diluent. This measurement was done using a Varian-4502 spectrometer and DPPH was used as internal standard. Infrared spectrum was recorded in KBr disc using a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complex is soluble in alcohol, acetone and acetonitrile to impart orange colour and insoluble in petroleum ether. In methanol, the complex is found to be non-electrolytic in nature ($\Lambda_M = 17.3 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The μ_{eff} value of 1.73 B.M. at 303K for the complex and 'g' value of 1.990 of powdered compound ($g_{\text{I}} = 1.997$ and $g_{\text{II}} = 1.982$ for esr spectrum of the compound diluted with KBr), is consistent with a low-spin d^5 configuration of Cr^{I} ^{6,7}. Its ir spectrum shows a very strong band⁸ at 1705 cm^{-1} (NO^+). The broad bands at 3540 and 3480 cm^{-1} and the shoulder at 1620 cm^{-1} are due to ν_{OH} and $\delta_{\text{H-O-H}}$, respectively. The bands at 620 and 575 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cr-N}}$ and $\delta_{\text{Cr-N-O}}$, respectively as reported by Miki⁹ and the author⁵. The band at 1490 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and single band at 995 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{O-S}}$ are indicative of the bidentate coordination of dithiocarbamate ligand¹⁰. On the basis of above data, an octahedral structure may be proposed for the complex.

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Kinetics of Chromic Acid Oxidation of Some Hydroxy Acids

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THE chromic acid oxidation of some hydroxy acids have been studied earlier¹⁻³. The kinetics of chromic acid oxidation of hydroxy acid having a substituent on the α -carbon have been reported⁴⁻⁷. But the reports do not reveal the process of oxidation of hydroxy acids by chromium(VI). This paper reports the results of the process of oxidation of hydroxy acids by chromium(VI).

Experimental

The hydroxy acids were of A.R. grade and the other chemicals including $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ were of G.R. (E. Merck) grade. 60% HClO_4 (E. Merck) was used as the source of hydrogen ion. The solvents were purified by standard procedures.

Kinetic measurements: The rate of consumption of Cr^{VI} was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the optical density on a Backman DU spectrophotometer at different intervals. In some cases the consumption of Cr^{VI} was determined iodometrically^{2,8-10}. Some experiments, under identical conditions, were conducted both iodometrically and

spectrophotometrically and the results agreed well within $\pm 1\%$ accuracy. In the spectrophotometric study the temperature was kept constant by circulating water from a thermostat. The ionic strength and $[H^+]$ were kept much higher than that of the oxidant. The rate constant was calculated from the plots of $\log [Cr^{VI}]$ vs time (t) and the values were reproducible within $\pm 2\%$ accuracy.

Identification of oxidation product: The reaction products, aldehydes and ketones were identified by preparing their 2,4-DNP derivatives. Aldehyde was detected by its specific chromotropic acid test. The derivatives of the products were extracted with ethyl acetate and then with aqueous Na_2CO_3 (10%) which on adding KOH solution (2.5 N) turned red. The red solution gave λ_{max} at 350 nm similar to an authentic solution of hydroxy acids.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying $[H^+]$, added salt, reagent and temperature: The reaction was studied at varying reagent concentration and the order with respect to oxidant was found to be one. The first order rate constant (k_1) showed that k_1 decreases with increasing the initial $[Cr^{VI}]$. This suggests that $HCrO_4^-$ is the reacting species^{11,12} of Cr^{VI} . The rate of oxidation increased with the increasing concentration of the substrate.

In order to study the effect of $[H^+]$ the experiments were carried out at different $HClO_4$ concentrations while keeping the $[hydroxy\ acid]_0$ and $[Cr^{VI}]_0$ constant. The result shows a proportional dependence on first power of $[H^+]$ concentration (Table 1) at constant ionic strength (NaCl). The plots of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$ are found to be linear in the case of salicylic acid and phenyl salicylate where the slopes were significantly less than one.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING $[H^+]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 22°

$[Cr^{VI}] = 2.52 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $\mu = 0.72$ for salicylic and phenylsalicylate; $[Cr^{VI}] = 2.49 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 1.27$ for tartaric acid

$[H^+]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹	$k_1/[H^+]$ 1 mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
[Tartaric acid] = $10.6 \times 10^{-2} M$		
1.0	2.63 ± 0.14	1.87
2.00	3.40 ± 0.27	1.73
2.60	4.08 ± 0.30	1.56
3.00	4.17 ± 0.36	1.39
[Salicylic acid] = $1.17 \times 10^{-2} M$		
0.17	7.91 ± 0.68	—
0.21	9.87 ± 0.85	—
0.31	11.12 ± 0.96	—
0.42	12.48 ± 0.10	—
[Phenylsalicylate] = $1.75 \times 10^{-2} M$		
0.17	6.79 ± 0.42	—
0.21	8.52 ± 0.52	—
0.31	9.42 ± 0.72	—
0.42	10.53 ± 0.86	—

All the reactions are of ionic dipole type. It was found that the rates increased with increasing ionic strength. The first order rate, however, decreased with increasing ionic strength (NaCl). The tendency of rate to remain constant at higher ionic strength (NaCl), may be attributed to the ion-association together with the cage effect which restrain dissociation of ion-pair Na^+Cl^- effectively, thus nullifying its effect on the reaction rate.

The first order rate constants were determined at different temperatures (25-35°) and the activation parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ for phenylsalicylate, salicylic, gallic and tartaric acids were evaluated.

The plots of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta H^\ddagger$ are linear except in the case of tartaric acid. The oxidation of tartaric acid by H_2CrO_4 ions probably accounts for the anomalous behaviour of tartaric acid. The mechanism of oxidation of tartaric acid is, therefore, expected to be different in this case. The results suggest that $HCrO_4^-$ is probably the reacting species. However, attempts were made to check the constancy of $K[Cr^{VI}]/[HCrO_4^-]$ in the case of hydroxy acids. The reaction rate increases with the increasing $[Cr^{VI}]$ in the case of tartaric acid. This may be due to the fact that the reacting species of chromium in this case is different, and not $HCrO_4^-$.

The transfer of three electrons to Cr^{VI} for the overall reactions does not take place in one step, either they are transferred one by one or by two electron transfer process. In these cases of acid catalysed reactions, proton may either add on to the substrate to give protonated substrate followed by reaction of the latter with $HCrO_4^-$ to give reaction products according to steps (1) and (2), or it may be addition to $HCrO_4^-$ to give H_2CrO_4 followed by its reaction with the substrate according to steps (3) and (4).

where S is substrate and P* is product.

The formation of protonated substrate seems unlikely, since water is more basic than hydroxy acids. On the other hand, the H_2CrO_4 is highly ionised species and its reaction with hydroxy acid seems unlikely. The collision number of these reactions are much less than 10^{11} suggesting that the reactions are not of bimolecular type. The kinetics evidence indicates that 1 : 1 intermediate compounds are formed in the case of reaction of salicylic acid and phenylsalicylate with $HCrO_4^-$, since, the plots of $1/k$ vs $1/[substrate]$ are linear passing through the origin. This is in contrast to the oxidation of gallic, glycollic and benzoic acids. Both the kinetic

and spectrophotometric results indicate the formation of intermediate complex between Cr^{VI} and hydroxy acid.

It may be also mentioned here that unlike glycollic acid, C—H bond on the carbon atom is absent in salicylic and phenylsalicylate which form complexes with divalent and trivalent transition metal ions. The reaction may be explain on the basis of the formation of free radicals, e.g. RR'C(OH), which reacts with Cr^{VI} to form stable products ketone and Cr^{VI}, may be considered as

The formation of free radicals, however, could not be detected, since all the experiments are performed in the presence of air. The presence of intermediate valence states of chromium has been indicated by the decrease in the reaction rate in the presence of manganese(II). The appreciable increase in the reaction rate on adding bidentate ligands (Table 4) has been explained due to a two electron transfer reaction which have been observed by us.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF OXIDATION OF HYDROXY ACIDS BY Cr^{VI}

Acid	ΔH‡ k cal mol ⁻¹	—ΔS‡ e. u.	ΔG‡ at 303 K k cal
Salicylic acid	18.5 ± 1.8	13.6 ± 4.6	22.6 ± 2.4
Phenylsalicylate	17.8 ± 2.0	13.12 ± 2.5	21.7 ± 1.5
Gallic acid	15.6 ± 1.3	32.2 ± 2.8	25.27 ± 1.2
Tartaric acid	22.2 ± 2.2	4.03 ± 3.2	23.43 ± 0.8

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF Mn^{II} ION ON REACTION

[Mn ²⁺]	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	(a)	(b)
2.0	1.33 ± 0.92	4.57 ± 0.38
3.0	1.7 ± 0.90	4.24 ± 0.30
(a) [Tartaric acid] = 3.9 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 1.39 M.		
(b) [Gallic acid] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 1.27 M.		

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOME BIDENTATE LIGANDS ON REACTION RATE

2,2'-dipyridyl	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	(a)	(b)
1.0	5.07 ± 0.45	5.94 ± 0.42
2.0	5.41 ± 0.40	6.87 ± 0.54
(a) [Tartaric acid] = 1.5 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 2.54 M.		
(b) [Gallic acid] = 1.5 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ , [H ⁺] = 1.27 M.		

The course of reduction has been represented as Cr^{VI} → Cr^{IV} → Cr^{III}.

Moreover, it has been observed that some hydroxy acids react with the ions of transition metals to give stable 1 : 2 coordination compounds in solution. Consequently, the formation of 1 : 2 intermediate compound seems unlikely in the present study. The first order rate constants in the presence of Mn^{II} ion were found to be 1.3 × 10⁴, 1.7 × 10⁴ for tartaric acid and 4.57 × 10⁴, 4.24 × 10⁴ for gallic acid. This shows that the rate determining steps is also possibly by a two electron transfer process.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ionisation Constants of Hydroxytriazenes

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻³ have used spectrophotometric method for the determination of ionisation constants of some hydroxytriazenes. The present communication reports the ionisation constants of seven new hydroxytriazenes derived from 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene.